

ISic0411

Fragmentary text of the colonia Syacusanorum

Language

Latin

Type

honorific; building?

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

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Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [c]olonia I[]

2. [S]yracusanor[um]

3. [] IIII []AN

4. [] N CUR []NA

5. concordia grati

Apparatus

Text of CIL

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491643

EDCS 21900473

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7131 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650767>)

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